

Fabrication and Characterisation of Ligand- Functionalised Ultrapure Monodispersed Metal Nanoparticles Nanoassemblies Employing Advanced Gas Deposition Technique

Tesfalem Geremariam Welearegay^{1,2,3}, Umut Cindemir^{2,3}, Lars Österlund^{2,3}, Radu
Ionescu^{1,*}

¹ *Department of Electronics, Electrical and Automatic Engineering, Rovira i Virgili
University, Tarragona 43007, Spain.*

² *Molecular Fingerprint Sweden AB, Uppsala 75655, Sweden.*

³ *The Angstrom Laboratory, Department of Engineering Sciences, Uppsala University,
Uppsala 75121, Sweden.*

* Corresponding author. Email: radu.ionescu@urv.cat

Abstract

Here we report for the first time the fabrication of ligand functionalised ultrapure monodispersed metal nanoparticles (Au, Cu, and Pt) from their pure metal precursors using the Advanced Gas Deposition technique. The experimental conditions during nanoparticles formation were adjusted in order to obtain ultrafine isolated nanoparticles on different substrates. The morphology and surface analysis of the as-deposited metal

nanoparticles were investigated using Scanning Electron Microscopy, X-ray Diffraction and Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy, which demonstrated the formation of highly ordered pure crystalline nanoparticles with a relatively uniform size distribution of ~10 nm (Au), ~ 4 nm (Cu) and ~ 3 nm (Pt), respectively. A broad range of organic ligands containing thiol or amine functional groups were attached to the nanoparticles to form continuous networks of nanoparticle-ligand nanoassemblies, which were characterised by Scanning Electron Microscopy and X-Ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy. The electrical resistance of the functional nanoassemblies deposited in the gap spacing of two microfabricated parallel Au electrodes patterned on silicon substrates ranged between tens of $k\Omega$ and tens of $M\Omega$, which is suitable for uses in many applications including (bio)chemical sensors, surface enhanced Raman spectroscopy and molecular electronic rectifiers.

1. Introduction

Metal nanoparticles (MNP) have unique properties such as very high surface area to volume ratio as compared with the bulk metals, high surface energies, specific electronic structure, localised surface plasmon polaritons and quantum confinement [1]. These unique functional properties propelled their use in numerous applications in fields like catalysis [2], biomedicine [3], nanophotonics [4], optoelectronics [5], and sensors [6].

A large number of MNP (Au, Cu, Pt, Pd, Ag, Fe, Zn, Cd) can be nowadays synthesized through different preparation routes, including chemical methods (*e.g.*, chemical reduction of metal salts [7, 8], sonochemical reduction [9], chemical vapour deposition [10], microemulsions [11], supercritical fluids [12, 13], electrochemical synthesis [14]) and physical methods (physical vapour deposition [10, 15], microwave irradiation [16], pulsed laser deposition [17], thermal evaporation [15], gamma radiation [18, 19]). Nevertheless, these very versatile techniques give rise to traces of residual compounds remaining from the chemical precursors (in the case of the chemical methods) and/or produce uncontrolled particles size-distributions and aggregation (in the case of the physical methods).

The metal nanoparticles can be functionalised with different organic ligands for producing nanomaterials suitable for sensing applications, surface enhanced Raman spectroscopy (SERS), molecular electronic rectifiers, catalysis, and biomedical applications [20, 21]. The widely employed method for the fabrication of monolayer-capped metallic nanoparticles is based on the wet-chemistry technique that employs chemical precursors [22], which leaves traces of residual compounds in the nanomaterial produced [23].

In order to achieve the fabrication of ultrapure monodispersed metal nanoparticles, we have recently introduced an innovative technique based on Advanced Gas Deposition

(AGD), which we demonstrated for the fabrication of ultrapure and ultrafine gold nanoparticles (AuNPs) from a gold metal precursor [24]. The AGD process allows for log-normal size distribution of the nanoparticles, and monodisperse, ultrapure nanoparticles can be produced. Therefore, the nanoparticles are less prone to agglomeration and coalescence, which are the major problems in the case of the MNP prepared by other physical methods [25, 26].

In our previous study, the functionalisation of the ultrapure monodispersed AuNPs produced by AGD with dodecanethiol by dip-coating linked the nanoparticles in a metal-organic nanoassembly with novel characteristics, which yielded the first ever observation of Schottky-diodes fabricated from nanomaterials based on metal nanoparticles [24].

In the present paper, we demonstrate the versatility of the AGD technique for the synthesis of different ultrapure ultrafine MNP from their metal precursors (in particular we focus here on Au, Pt and Cu, but this technique can be extended to practically any other metal), and the suitability of the as-produced nanoparticles to be functionalised with a broad range of organic materials containing thiol or amine functional groups for the formation of self-assembled metal-organic monolayers.

2. Methods

Three different MNP (AuNPs, PtNPs and CuNPs) were directly generated from their pure metal precursors and deposited on different substrates by the advanced non-reactive gas deposition technique (Ultra Fine Particle Equipment, ULVAC Ltd, Japan [26]). The AGD setup adopted in this study for the fabrication of ultrapure monodispersed metal nanoparticles is shown in figure S1 from Supplementary Data. High purity metal pieces of gold (99.999 % purity), platinum wire (99.99 % purity), and copper pellets (99.99 % purity), were used as precursors for nanoparticles synthesis.

Before starting the deposition process, the two AGD chambers were evacuated by means of several oil pumps until their pressure reached ~ 0.02 mbar, in order to eliminate all the impurities from the equipment. After that their pressures were set to the adequate values that were determined for each metal in part (details are provided in the Results and discussion section), being the lower chamber kept at higher pressure (adjusted for each MPN formation) and the upper chamber at lower pressure (~ 0.09 mbar) during metal nanoparticles synthesis.

By applying a suitable power to the induction coil surrounding the metal source (4 kW for Au, 12 kW for Pt, and 3 kW for Cu), the metal precursor started to melt. The vapour zone formed above the molten metal consisted of metal atoms that gradually cooled down while they diffused through the He carrier gas introduced underneath the heated metal piece at a flow rate of 20 L/min, which carried them upwards. As the metal atoms experienced several collisions with each other, they started to agglomerate in such a way that nanoparticles were formed, leading to the nucleation and growth of ultrafine metal nanoparticles in the lower chamber. The stream of ultrafine nanoparticles generated in the lower chamber was then propelled to the upper chamber through the thin transfer pipe (3 mm diameter), which was heated by applying 40 kW power for avoiding condensations on its walls. Due to the pressure difference between the two chambers, the metal nanoparticles impinged at high speed onto the deposition substrate placed on the movable support, and got sticky deposited on it. The speed of the movable support and the number of deposition cycles (*i.e.*, number of times that the stream of nanoparticles impinged onto the substrate during its movement inside the upper AGD chamber) were optimised to obtain a monolayer of dispersed metal nanoparticles.

In the next experimental step, the metal nanoparticles as-deposited by AGD were functionalised with a broad range of organic ligands with different carbon chains (C3 to

C18), tail structures, and head groups (either thiol or amine), for promoting the formation of MNP-organic nanoassemblies through the nanoparticles-ligand interactions [27, 28]. Most of the selected molecular ligands comprised either a long hydrocarbon chain or an aromatic ring in their tail, which enables the interaction between neighbouring tails, while the thiol or amine head groups provide binding affinity with MNP surface [29]. The ligands were selected such as to cover a wide range of possible tail functional groups, head groups and chain lengths, for assessing the ability of the MNP fabricated by AGD to build strong and stable self-assembled MNP-organic ligand nanoassemblies. The following four groups of organic ligand were totally employed:

- I) Ligands with non-polar hydrocarbon chain in their tail and a thiol head group: **(A)** 2-butanethiol (2-BUT), **(B)** 1-decanethiol (1-DT), **(C)** 1-dodecanethiol (1-DDT);
- II) Ligands with non-polar aromatic ring in their tail and a thiol head group: **(D)** 4-methoxy- α -toluenethiol (4-MTT), **(E)** 2-mercaptobenzoxazole (2-MBZO);
- III) Ligands with hydrocarbon chain and polar functionality in their tail and a thiol head group: **(F)** 11-mercaptoundecanol (11-MUD), **(G)** 11-mercaptoundecanoic acid (11-MUDA), **(H)** methyl-3-mercaptopropionate (MMPP);
- IV) Ligand with long hydrophobic chain with non-polar tail and amine head group: **(I)** oleylamine (ODA).

The structure of the selected organic ligands is shown in figure 1. All chemicals employed for nanoparticles functionalisation were of analytical grade and used as received. 1-dodecanethiol: $\text{CH}_3(\text{CH}_2)_{11}\text{SH}$ (98% purity), 4-methoxy- α -toluenethiol: $\text{CH}_3\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{CH}_2\text{SH}$ (90% purity), oleylamine: $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{35}\text{NH}_2$ (98% purity), 2-mercaptobenzoxazole: $\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{NOS}$ (99% purity), 11-mercaptoundecanoic acid: $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_2\text{S}$ (98% purity), 1-butanethiol: $\text{CH}_3(\text{CH}_2)_3\text{SH}$ (99% purity), 1-decanethiol: $\text{CH}_3(\text{CH}_2)_9\text{SH}$ (96% purity), methyl-3-mercaptopropionate: $\text{HSC}_4\text{H}_5\text{O}_2$ (98% purity), 11-mercapto-1-

undecanol: HO(CH₂)₉SH (97% purity), ethanol (99.5% purity), chloroform (99% purity), acetone (95% purity) and isopropanol (96%) were purchased from Sigma Aldrich.

Figure 1. Molecular structure of the organic ligands used in this study for MNP functionalization.

For MNP functionalization, dissolutions were prepared as follows: 100 μ L of 2-butanethiol, 1-decanethiol, 1-dodecanethiol, oleylamine, 4-methoxy- α -toluenethiol and methyl-3-mercaptopropionate (liquid in their normal state) were dissolved in 20 mL ethanol; 10 mg of 11-mercaptoundecanoic acid and 75 mg of 2-mercaptobenzoxazole (solid in their normal state) were dissolved in 20 mL of ethanol; and 5 mg of 11 mercapto-1-undecanol (solid in its normal state) was dissolved in 5 mL of chloroform. The dissolutions were stirred with a magnetic stirrer for 30 min at room temperature to ensure homogeneity.

The dip coating method was then employed for the functionalisation of the as-deposited metal nanoparticles with the organic ligands. The substrates with the metal nanoparticles

deposited by AGD were dipped into the dissolution of each ligand for one hour, and then the substrates were dried in an oven for one hour at 50 °C with a ramp of 10 °C/min to ensure solvent evaporation. This process was repeated several times until a self-assembled MNP-organic ligand monolayer was formed, and the electrical resistance of the nanoassembly formed between two 15 µm gaped parallel gold electrodes patterned by chemical etching on one side polished p-type <100> Si substrates (13×8 mm²) (*see* Supplementary data, figure S3) measured a value in the kΩ to MΩ range.

Nanomaterials characterisation was carried out both after metal nanoparticles deposition by AGD, as well as after nanoparticles functionalisation with the organic ligands. Morphology and surface analysis studies were performed with a Zeiss LEO 1550 High Resolution Scanning Electron Microscope (HR-SEM), using a field emission gun as electron source, an acceleration voltage of 10 kV and high magnification values (300,000-1,000,000), and 1 nm resolution. The structure and phase orientation of the metal nanoparticles were acquired by X-ray Diffraction (XRD) using a Siemens D5000 equipment operated with CuK_α radiation (λ=1.54 Å). Crystallites size was calculated from the X-ray diffractograms by applying Scherrer's formula:

$$D = K\lambda/\beta\cos\theta,$$

where D is the volume-weighted average crystallite size, K is the Scherrer constant and takes into account the morphology of the crystallites ($K = 0.94$ corresponding to spherical crystallites was used here), λ is the x-ray wavelength, β is the peak width at Full width at Half Maximum (FWHM), and θ is the diffraction angle. The elemental and chemical composition of the nanoassemblies were characterised by X-Ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS) using a PHI Quantum 2000 equipment with an AlK_α X-ray energy source of 1486 eV having a beam diameter of 200 µm. Survey scans were measured with a pass energy of 58.7 eV and resolution of 1 eV where high resolution scans were

measured with a pass energy of 23.50 eV and 0.025 eV resolution. Energy range of the survey scans were 1100-0 eV. To control samples charging, a neutralizer filament was used in all measurements. CasaXPS software (version 2.3.16) was used for the spectral curve fittings, while the binding energies were referenced to the C1s of alkyl chains at 248.8 eV. The peaks were fitted with a Gaussian-Lorentzian function and Shirley type background. Raman Spectroscopic spectra of Cu₂O NPs thin films were performed using Raman FTIR (Leica DM 2500 equipment) with laser energy of 514 nm.

Glass substrates (76×26×1 mm³, Gerhard Menzel GmbH, Germany) were used for XRD and FTIR analysis, and single side polished 4-inch Si wafer with 1 μm thickness silicon oxide on top (Silicon Materials, Germany) for SEM and XPS analysis.

Before placing the Si substrates in the AGD equipment for nanoparticles synthesis, they were cleaned by successive wash in an ultrasonic bath for 5 min in propanol and acetone, followed by rinsing with deionised water and drying with blowing nitrogen flow. When the silicon substrates with the patterned gold electrodes were employed, the substrate was covered with a special tape that left uncovered only the gap between the gold electrodes for the deposition of the nanoparticles exclusively in between them.

The electrical resistance of the MNP-ligand nanoassemblies was measured between the two parallel gold electrodes with a high-precision Keysight power source (B2902A, Keysight Technologies, Hungary), using an internal applied voltage of 1V. The I-V characteristic curves were measured by supplying a sweeping voltage between -10V and 10V between the two gold electrodes, at a sweep rate of 0.1 V/sec, and acquiring the current between the electrodes.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Fabrication and characterisation of monodispersed metal nanoparticles

For each MNP, the different deposition parameters – pressure of the two AGD chambers; inductive heating power for melting the pure metal precursor; laminar flow rate of He carrier gas; speed and number of deposition cycles of the movable support where the deposition substrate was placed – were adjusted in function of the metal employed, for the adequate growth and formation of dispersed isolated metal nanoparticles onto the substrate.

For AuNPs synthesis, by optimising the pressure in the evaporation chamber of the AGD equipment at 90.8 mbar, the formation of monodispersed AuNPs was achieved during one deposition cycle for the speed of the movable support set to 1 mm/sec (figure 2(a)). The increase of the pressure in the evaporation chamber to 100 mbar favoured to the formation of small islands of AuNPs because of the tendency of the nanoparticles to agglomerate due to Van der Waals interactions occurring between them at this higher pressure, which led to the deposition of small aggregates of NPs even at the highest speed of the movable support (2.5 mm/sec), set in order to minimise the deposition time of the AuNPs onto the substrate (figure 2(b)). Importantly, the size and shape of the nanoparticles did not change by modifying the pressure in the evaporation chamber, as it can be seen by the closer examination of the isolated AuNPs in figure 2(b), which were very similar with those in figure 2(a). Further increase of the number of deposition cycles led to the formation of continuous networks of linked AuNPs (figure 2(c)). A continuous thin film of AuNPs that fully covered the substrate (~ 30 nm thicknesses) was achieved by increasing the deposition time through lowering the speed of the movable support to 1.25 mm/sec (figure 2(d)). Particles size distribution displayed in figure 2(e) shows that the monodispersed AuNPs have a normal distribution, with a mean diameter of 9.7 ± 0.1 nm. The XRD spectra acquired on the thin AuNPs film, depicted in figure 2(f), exhibited diffraction peaks at 2θ diffraction angles of $\sim 38.3^\circ$, 44.4° , 64.8° and 77.8° , which were

indexed to the (1 1 1), (2 0 0), (2 2 0) and (3 1 1) planes corresponding to face-centred cubic (fcc) Au (ICCD: 04-003.5615). A very strong intensity peak for Au (1 1 1) plane was observed at $2\theta \sim 38.3^\circ$, while weak intensity peaks were observed for Au (2 0 0) and Au (2 2 0) planes, which corresponds to the formation of pure crystalline AuNPs in agreement with that of Au in its elemental state. The mean crystallites size of the AuNPs calculated using Scherrer's equation applied to the Au (1 1 1) peak at 38.3° was found to be ~ 10.7 nm, which is in good agreement with the particles size distribution obtained from the SEM image of monodispersed AuNPs. This finding further confirmed that the size of the nanoparticles deposited by AGD does not change as a function of coverage, and even in the limit of a dense film the MNP size is maintained.

Figure 2. SEM images of the AuNPs synthesised using the following experimental parameters of AGD (pressure in the evaporation chamber, speed of the movable support, and number of deposition cycles): (a) 90.8 mbar, 1 mm/sec, 1 cycle; (b) 100 mbar, 2.5 mm/sec, 1 cycle; (c) 100 mbar, 2.5 mm/sec, 3 cycles; (d) 100 mbar, 1.25 mm/sec, 3 cycles. (e) Histogram of particles size distribution for the SEM image shown in figure 2(a). (f) X-ray diffractogram of the AuNPs thin film shown in figure 2(d).

The deposition conditions determined for the synthesis of dispersed AuNPs were next applied for the generation and deposition of platinum nanoparticles (PtNPs) from their pure metal precursor. However, a higher induction heating power was needed for the generation of PtNPs because of the considerable higher melting point of Pt (1768 °C) as compared with Au (1064 °C). Because of the different chemical and physical characteristics of the two metals, including saturated vapour pressure and melting temperature, a quasi-continuous thin film of PtNPs was formed (figure 3(a)). The shape and particles size depend on the heating temperature, molecular weight, total pressure and flow rate of the inert gas [26]. Therefore, the size and distribution of the PtNPs deposited by AGD were different from those of the AuNPs employing the same experimental conditions – with the exception of the higher heating induction power. The mean PtNPs size calculated from the histogram of the PtNPs shown in figure 3(a) was found to be 3.0 ± 0.1 nm, while the narrow size distribution of the nanoparticles exhibited a statistical log-normal distribution (*see* figure 3(b)), as it is commonly observed in the case of nanoparticles evaporated in an inert gas [26]. Because of the low diffusion rate of the Pt atoms into the He carrier gas, Pt particles nucleation and growth was rather limited, leading to the synthesis of ultrafine PtNPs of extremely small size. The X-ray diffractogram of the PtNPs thin film shown in figure 3(a), depicted in figure 3(c), indicated four peaks attributed to four different crystalline phases of Pt at $2\theta \sim 39.8^\circ$, 46.2° , 67.4° and 81.2° , indexed as (1 1 1), (2 0 0), (2 2 0) and (3 1 1) planes, respectively (ICCD: 04-001-0112). The spectra exhibiting a strong diffraction peak at $\sim 39.8^\circ$ depicted the deposition of pure crystalline PtNPs with a preferred growth orientation of Pt (1 1 1). The broadening and weak intensities of the other three diffraction peaks suggested relatively small surface density and particles size. Applying Scherrer's formula to the (1

1) peak, the mean crystallites size was calculated as ~ 3 nm, which is in excellent agreement with the mean Pt particles size estimated from the SEM analysis.

Figure 3. (a) SEM image of the PtNPs deposited by AGD using the following processing parameters: 90.8 mbar pressure in the evaporation chamber; 1 mm/sec speed of the movable support; 1 deposition cycle. (b) Histogram of Pt nanoparticles size distribution calculated from figure 3(a). (c) XRD spectra acquired on the PtNPs thin film shown in figure 3(a).

Finally, the same experimental conditions were employed for the generation and deposition of copper nanoparticles (CuNPs). As copper has a melting point (1085°C) close to the gold (1064°C), similar characteristics were expected for the CuNPs, comparable with those of the AuNPs. However, the vapour region formed above the melted Cu precursor contained a very low concentration of Cu atoms in the He carrier gas where particles nucleation and growth took place. For this reason, barely few nanoparticles were deposited on the substrate. In order to enhance particles nucleation, the pressure in the evaporation chamber was increased to 94 mbar. Figure 4(a) shows the SEM image of the thin film formed on the substrate when the pressure in the evaporation chamber was set to 94 mbar. This figure revealed the deposition of a continuous layer of ultrafine particles of extremely small grain size. The CuNPs, moreover, showed to be partly oxidised under the low vacuum conditions employed in AGD, and a thin oxide protective layer was inferred from XRD and FTIR studies. This is not surprising

considering that Cu is known to be highly susceptible to oxidation [30]. The histogram of particles size distribution indicated a mean particles size of 2 ± 0.05 nm, with narrow size and statistical log-normal distribution (figure 4(b)), similar to the case of PtNPs. The structure and surface analysis of the thin film shown in figure 4(a) was next characterised by XRD. The diffraction peaks acquired, shown in figure 4(c), confirmed the formation of both metallic CuNPs and cuprous oxide (Cu_2O). The diffractogram of the film analysed inferred six diffraction patterns, with 2θ diffraction angles at $\sim 29.9^\circ$, 36.9° , 43.3° , 50.4° , 62.2° and 74.1° , indexed with the Cu_2O (1 1 0), Cu_2O (1 1 1), Cu (1 1 1), Cu (2 0 0), Cu_2O (2 0 0) and Cu_2O (3 1 1) planes characteristic for metal copper and its Cu_2O oxide, respectively (ICDD:04-006-5764; ICDD:04-004-7864) [31, 32]. The strong diffraction peaks observed at $2\theta \sim 36.9^\circ$ and 43.3° exhibited characteristic peaks corresponding to cuprous oxide and metallic Cu in their (1 1 1) preferred crystallite phase orientation. The weak intensity peak at 74.1° where Cu (2 2 0) and Cu_2O (3 1 1) crystal planes overlapped, confirming the coexistence of both metallic CuNPs and cuprous oxide. In conclusion, the XRD analysis revealed the generation and deposition of ultrafine single crystalline metallic CuNPs and Cu_2O nanoparticles. No characteristic peaks of cupric oxide (CuO) were observed in the XRD pattern, indicating the formation of an ultrapure nanocrystalline thin film. The mean crystallites size of the nanoparticles, calculated using Scherrer's formula applied to the (2θ) peaks at $\sim 36.9^\circ$ and 43.3° , were found to be ~ 4 nm and ~ 4.5 nm for CuNPs and Cu_2O , respectively. The difference between crystallites size calculated by applying Scherrer's formula and the mean particles size estimated from the SEM histogram presented in figure 4(b) come from the level of SEM resolution. Raman spectroscopy studies ascertained the formation of cuprous oxide layer at the surface of the metallic copper nanoparticles. The corresponding Raman spectra shown in figure 4(d) revealed a composite $\text{Cu}_2\text{O}/\text{CuNPs}$ film exhibiting characteristic Cu Raman

peaks at 148 cm^{-1} and 213 cm^{-1} , and peaks at 530 cm^{-1} and 628 cm^{-1} that were assigned to the Cu_2O phase [33]. No Raman bands were recorded above 800 cm^{-1} , which further indicates that no other oxides were formed.

Figure 4. (a) SEM image of CuNPs deposited by AGD using the following processing parameters: 94 mbar pressure of the evaporation chamber, 1 mm/sec speed of the movable support, 1 deposition cycle. (b) Histogram of Cu nanoparticles size distribution calculated from figure 4(a). (c) XRD spectra acquired on the CuNPs thin film shown in figure 4(a). (d) Raman spectra of the CuNPs film showing traces of Cu_2O layer.

3.2. MNP Functionalisation with Organic Ligands and Nanoassemblies Characterisation

MNP functionalisation with the organic ligands allowed modifying MNP surface without introducing surfactants as in the case of the two phase transfer based surface modification methods [34].

In the case of AuNPs, the functionalisation was performed on the monodispersed AuNPs structure shown in figure 2(a), while in the case of PtNPs and CuNPs, ligand bonding was done on the structures shown in figures 3(a) and 4(a), respectively. The ligands bounded through the thiol or amine head groups to the free regions of the MNP not attached to the substrate, available for molecules attachment. The capping ligands under study had distinct characteristics, which produced different nanoassemblies structures and different surface coverage for each ligand, which are summarised in table 1.

Organic ligand	AuNPs	PtNPs	CuNPs
2-BUT	Clusters network, low coverage (24%)	No ligand capping	No ligand capping
1-DT	Linked nanoparticles network, low coverage (26%)	No ligand capping	Well ordered, medium coverage (60%)
1-DDT	Well ordered, low coverage (34%)	Medium coverage (56%)	Clusters network, low coverage (37%)
4-MTT	High coverage (86%)	Medium coverage (58%)	Medium coverage (55%)
2-MBZO	Short-linked clusters network, high coverage (84%)	Isolated clusters, low coverage (29%)	Well ordered, medium coverage (51%)
11-MUD	Low coverage (18%)	No ligand capping	Low coverage (16%)
11-MUDA	Low coverage (24%)	High coverage (71%)	Medium coverage (66%)
MMPP	Low coverage (20%)	Medium coverage (53%)	No ligand capping
ODA	Low coverage (25%)	Isolated clusters, low coverage (42%)	Low coverage (26%)

Table 1. MNP-ligand nanoassemblies characteristics. Low coverage refers to surface coverage below 50%; medium coverage to surface coverage between 50% and 70%, and high coverage to surface coverage over 70%. Surface coverage calculation is presented in Section 2 from Supplementary data.

The morphology of the nanoassemblies characterised by SEM is presented in figure 5 for some of the organic ligands.

In the case of AuNPs functionalisation, all ligands were able to bind the surface of the AuNPs, producing self-assembled monolayer nanoassemblies after a single or several dipping processes into the ligand dissolution. It is assumed that the monodispersed AuNPs provided surface interactions for the ligands through their head group, while the tail-tail interactions of neighbouring ligands completed the network. The self-assembly of the alkanethiols was driven by the strong affinity between the sulphur and the gold, with Van der Waals interactions between the alkyl (aromatic) chains, and dipole interactions between the polar end groups.

Figure 5(a) displays a well-ordered self-assembled monolayer of 1-dodecanethiol linking the AuNPs, which fairly covered the surface of the base substrate, while figure 5(b) depicts a denser monolayer of 4-methoxy- α -toluenethiol chemisorbed onto AuNPs surfaces. These two ligands most likely exhibited strong attachment on AuNPs surfaces and achieved tail to tail hydrogen bonding with the neighbouring attached ligands. Figure 5(c) also demonstrates a high density self-assembled monolayer for 2-mercaptobenzoxazole bonded on AuNPs surfaces. The ligands 4-MTT and 2-MBZO consisted of polar aromatic ring structures in their tail, and multiple H-bonding might have been developed between neighbouring molecules leading to well-ordered self-assembled monolayer nanoassemblies (figures 5(b-c)). Figure 5(d) shows the formation of a less-ordered monolayer with low surface coverage when the AuNPs were capped with 1-decanethiol, probably due to the steric stability of the NPs that drastically reduced the surface charge interactions towards the thiol, avoiding strong covalent bonding.

In the case of PtNPs functionalisation, some organic ligands (MMPP, 11-MUDA, 4-MTT, and 1-DDT) could form quite dense and rather homogenous monolayers of PtNPs-

organic nanoassemblies, probably due to the extremely small crystallites sizes of PtNPs (3 nm mean diameter, in comparison with 10.7 nm for AuNPs), which influenced their interaction with the organic ligands. For the first three ligands, this might be explained as these molecular organic ligands contain either polar or aromatic tail and a thiol head group that was chemisorbed on the surface of the PtNPs, promoting stable NPs-ligand nanoassemblies with strong tail-tail electrostatic interactions and hydrogen-bonding. The adsorption of the non-polar 1-DDT on the surface of ultrafine PtNPs might be due to the compromise between the hydrocarbon chain length, suitable for the formation of a self-assembled monolayer, and the strong Pt-S interactions, leading to substantially stable NPs-ligand nanoassemblies. The organic ligands with hydrophobic and non-polar tail that did not form stable NPs-ligand nanoassemblies had shorter carbon chains that might have accommodated head-tail steric effects on the surface of the NPs (*see* figure 5(e) as a representative example for this case). Although presenting a similar structure with 11-MUDA, the less polar 11-MUD organic ligand has neither achieved suitable PtNPs linking.

For CuNPs functionalisation, all molecular ligands except 2-BUT led to the formation of NPs-organic nanoassemblies. The morphology of the CuNPs-organic nanoassemblies revealed the formation of a flatted ligand-nanoparticles layer (figure 5(f)). It is likely that the presence of the protective thin oxide layer on the nanoparticles surface enhanced the surface attachment of the ligands through $\text{Cu}_2\text{O-S}$, Cu-O=C and COO-Cu bonding in addition to the expected Cu-S attachment. In this case, the ligands might have multiple interactions through a strong H-bonding with the surface coating oxide and the NPs. In the case of 2-BUT, the failure of adequate ligand capping could be explained as the smaller C-

C chain length of this ligand was not suitable to maintain tail-to-tail networking able to form ligand-NPs nanoassemblies.

Interestingly, the CuNPs and PtNPs exhibited very different assembly patterns although their particle sizes were quite similar each other, which is attributed to the susceptibility to oxidation of the CuNPs surface exposed to environmental air, leading to composite Cu₂O/CuNPs films (*see figure 4*).

Figure 5. SEM images of self-assembled: (a) AuNPs capped with 1-DDT; (b) AuNPs capped with 4-MTT; (c) AuNPs capped with 2-MBZO; (d) AuNPs capped with 1-DT; (e) PtNPs capped with 1-BUT; (f) CuNPs capped with 2-MBZO.

XPS studies were performed to further investigate the elemental composition of the nanoassemblies surfaces. The elemental surface composition of the MNP before and after functionalisation with different organic ligands is represented in figure 6. PtNPs samples composition is not shown in figure 6 because the PtNPs were too small and the XPS elemental composition was mostly dominated by photoelectrons coming from the substrate atoms corresponding to Si and O.

Figure 6. Surface elemental composition calculated from the XPS spectra for: (a) AuNPs and various AuNPs-ligand nanoassemblies; (b) CuNPs, and both CuNPs-ligand and PtNPs-ligand nanoassemblies.

As representative examples of AuNPs-ligand nanoassemblies, figure 7 shows the XPS spectra of the AuNPs capped with three organic ligands (1-DDT, 4-MTT and 2-MBZO). The XPS spectra of these films are consistent with the successful functionalisation of the AuNPs with the organic ligands, as manifested by the signal intensity of each core level region in each sample. Due to samples exposure to air, the XPS spectra revealed detectable oxygen in all MNP-ligand nanoassemblies in addition to oxygen coming from the SiO₂/Si base substrate.

Figure 7. High resolution XPS spectra acquired for the AuNPs nanoassemblies capped with: 1-DDT (black); 4-MTT (red); 2-MBZO (blue).

The elemental surface characterisation of the nanoassembly formed by the PtNPs capped with 11-MUDA is shown in figure 8 as a representative example of the self-assembled PtNPs-organic monolayers. The XPS spectra of this nanoassembly exhibited the presence of core-level spectra of Pt4f, C1s, S2p and O1s, which originated from the PtNPs and the corresponding adsorbed ligand, respectively. The XPS signal for Si2p is associated with the uncovered SiO₂/Si substrate where the nanoparticles were deposited and functionalised.

Figure 8. High resolution XPS spectra acquired for the PtNPs capped with 11-MUDA.

The elemental surface analysis of the CuNPs-organic nanoassemblies revealed that, in general, the sulphur S2p signal was very weak due to inelastic scattering of S2p electrons by the molecules in the monolayer, and in some cases the metal-S covalent bonding resulted in partial oxidation at the metal-S interfaces mediated by the metal nanoparticles. The ultrafine Cu nanoparticles, however, exhibited high surface density atoms that enhanced the surface attachment of the organic ligands. XPS spectra of different CuNPs-organic nanoassemblies are presented in figure 9, for 11-MUDA, ODA and 2-MBZO capping. The acquired spectra illustrated that the surface density of the CuNPs-2-MBZO nanoassembly was much higher as compared with the CuNPs functionalised with 11-MUDA and ODA. This might be related to the surface charge density of the aromatic ring that electrostatically stabilised the small size CuNPs. Besides, the XPS surface analysis of the CuNPs-ODA and CuNPs-11-MUDA nanoassemblies presented very low percentages of

CuNPs, which was beyond the sensitivity of the device that was unable to recognise the surface electrons originated from the CuNPs.

Figure 9. High resolution XPS spectra of CuNPs capped with: oleylamine (ODA) (black), 2-mercaptobenzoxazole (2-MBZO) (blue), and 11-mercaptoundecanoic acid (11-MUDA) (red).

Deeper XPS investigations focussed on the elemental scans of the nanoassemblies surfaces are shown in Supplementary data, figures S4 to S8.

3.3. Electrical Characterisation of the Nanomaterials Produced

The electrical resistance of the MNP films deposited between two 15 μm gapped parallel gold electrodes patterned on Si substrates (*see* Methods section and Supplementary data, figure S3) was characterised after MNP deposition, and after MNP functionalisation with the different organic ligands.

No electrical current could be measured between the electrodes after the deposition of monodispersed MPN by AGD, which confirmed that the MNP were not linked with each other.

After MNP functionalisation, the self-assembled nanostructures generally formed uninterrupted core-shell nanoparticle-ligand networks that promoted an electric path between the electrodes [28]. Figure 10 displays the electrical resistance measured for all the nanoassemblies produced in this study; however, it is important to point out that the electrical properties of these nanoassemblies can be tuned by adjusting the fabrication parameters.

As depicted in figure 10, all capping ligands produced a continuous network of the self-assembled monolayer with the AuNPs (~ 10.7 nm mean diameter). Despite the smaller crystallites size of CuNPs (~ 4 nm mean diameter), most CuNPs-organic nanoassemblies exhibited an electrical resistances between the electrodes, while the nanoassemblies of monolayer-capped PtNPs (~ 3 nm mean diameter) were able to promote electronic conduction only for few organic ligands: MMPP, 11-MUDA, 4-MTT and 1-DDT. The electrical resistance of these films was lower, confirming the medium-high surface coverage presented in table 1. The robustness of the nanoassemblies developed in this study was evidenced by the small drift produced in the electrical resistance during one year period (below 12% for all nanomaterials).

Figure 10. Electrical resistance of all MNP-ligand nanoassemblies produced in this study.

In these MNP-ligand nanoassemblies, the MNP are assembled via organic molecules that act as interparticles mediators, and the conduction through these nanostructures is provided by the electron tunnelling mechanism throughout the nanoparticles-ligand network. The MNP provide the electronic charge, and electrons transport occurs by electrons jumping between neighbouring nanoparticles through the organic matrix [35, 36]. Even in the case of the long organic ligand that has no conjugation (*i.e.*, 11-MUDA), the carboxylic group from its tail could induce a chemical interaction with the tail of the neighbouring organic molecule, which linked the MNP and as a result an active percolation path was developed through the nanoassembly [37].

In accordance with previous findings [24], the monolayer-capped AuNPs, as well as the monolayer-capped PtNPs, showed a Schottky diode behaviour, while the monolayer-capped CuNPs showed a resistor behaviour that is attributed to the formation of the thin Cu₂O passivation layer on the nanoparticles surface (figure 11).

Figure 11. I-V characteristic curves of: (a) AuNPs capped with 2-MBZO; (b) PtNPs capped with 4-MTT; (c) CuNPs capped with 2-MBZO.

The electron transport through the nanoassemblies was promoted through the distribution of conducting paths of the core-shell network that is expanded between the two parallel electrodes. This configuration and the molecular MNP-organic nanoassemblies are of

high technological importance for different applications, and allows to considerably widen the variety of MNP-organic ligands combination that can be used as (bio)chemical sensors, SERS surfaces and molecular electronic rectifiers. As a non-exhaustive example, the sensing potential of one of the devices produced in this study is shown in figure 12.

Figure 12. Response of the CuNPs-dodecanethiol device to three successive exposures to synthetic air and exhaled breath samples of a smoker and a non-smoker individuals.

4. Conclusion

Ultrapure monodispersed metal nanoparticles of various metals (Au, Pt and Cu) were fabricated in a single step process from their pure metal precursors by the Advanced Gas Deposition technique. By employing this method, the major problem associated with nanoparticles tendency to aggregate that occurs in the case of other physical deposition techniques was avoided by the direct evaporation of the pure metal and nanoparticles growth by condensation under a high purity inert gas. We successfully synthesised and deposited on different substrates high quality ultrafine AuNPs, PtNPs and CuNPs (mean crystallites sizes: ~ 10.7 nm, 3 nm and 4 nm, respectively). The technique introduced can be easily extended to practically any MNP synthesis using the proper metal source and adjusting the synthesis parameters.

A broad range of organic ligands with different carbon chains, tail structures and head groups, were then used to functionalise the MNP by dip-coating the substrates in a dissolution formed in high purity reagents, which led to the formation of self-assembled nanoparticles-organic monolayers with a network-like structure. The MNP-ligand nanoassemblies presented hybrid characteristics, where the nanoparticles served for electrical conduction, while the capping organic molecule promoted electron tunnelling through the MNP, which produced a measurable resistance in the range of tens of $k\Omega$ to tens of $M\Omega$ for most of the nanoassemblies. The AuNPs and PtNPs nanoassemblies exhibited Schottky diode behaviour, while the CuNPs showed a resistor type conduction behaviour consistent with the thin oxide Cu_2O passivation layer formed on these CuNPs. These high-purity functional nanoassemblies could impart interesting chemical, physical and electrical properties, suitable for various applications such as (bio)chemical sensing, surface enhanced Raman spectroscopy or molecular electronic rectifiers, exemplified here by selective response towards breath samples detection. Importantly, the properties of these nanoassemblies can be tuned by properly adjusting the fabrications parameters.

Acknowledgements

T.G.W acknowledges a FPI predoctoral fellowship from MINECO (Spain). R.I. acknowledges a 'Ramón y Cajal' fellowship awarded by MINECO (Spain). The authors wish to thank Prof. Cristhian Manuel Duran-Acevedo (Universidad de Pamplona, Colombia) for performing the breath sensing test. This work was supported by EC's H2020 Program H2020-MSCA-RISE-2014, Grant Agreement No. 645758 – "TROPSENSE".

References

- [1] MIRELA D 2009 METALLIC NANOPARTICLES. UNIVERSITY OF NOVA GORICA)
- [2] Hrapovic S, Liu Y, Male K B and Luong J H 2004 Electrochemical biosensing platforms using platinum nanoparticles and carbon nanotubes *Analytical chemistry* **76** 1083-8
- [3] Dreaden E C, Alkilany A M, Huang X, Murphy C J and El-Sayed M A 2012 The golden age: gold nanoparticles for biomedicine *Chemical Society Reviews* **41** 2740-79
- [4] Kamat P V 2002 Photophysical, Photochemical and Photocatalytic Aspects of Metal Nanoparticles *The Journal of Physical Chemistry B* **106** 7729-44
- [5] Maier S A, Brongersma M L, Kik P G, Meltzer S, Requicha A A and Atwater H A 2001 Plasmonics—a route to nanoscale optical devices *Advanced Materials* **13** 1501-5
- [6] Segev-Bar M and Haick H 2013 Flexible sensors based on nanoparticles *ACS Nano* **7** 8366-78
- [7] Turkevich J, Stevenson P C and Hillier J 1951 A study of the nucleation and growth processes in the synthesis of colloidal gold *Discussions of the Faraday Society* **11** 55-75
- [8] Bönemann H and Richards Ryan M 2001 Nanoscopic Metal Particles – Synthetic Methods and Potential Applications *European Journal of Inorganic Chemistry* **2001** 2455-80
- [9] Okitsu K 2011 *Theoretical and Experimental Sonochemistry Involving Inorganic Systems*, ed M Ashokkumar (Dordrecht: Springer Netherlands) pp 131-50

- [10] Swihart M T 2003 Vapor-phase synthesis of nanoparticles *Current Opinion in Colloid & Interface Science* **8** 127-33
- [11] Capek I 2004 Preparation of metal nanoparticles in water-in-oil (w/o) microemulsions *Advances in Colloid and Interface Science* **110** 49-74
- [12] Zhang Y and Erkey C 2006 Preparation of supported metallic nanoparticles using supercritical fluids: A review *The Journal of Supercritical Fluids* **38** 252-67
- [13] Kim J, Kim D, Veriansyah B, Won Kang J and Kim J-D 2009 Metal nanoparticle synthesis using supercritical alcohol *Materials Letters* **63** 1880-2
- [14] Ma H, Yin B, Wang S, Jiao Y, Pan W, Huang S, Chen S and Meng F 2004 Synthesis of Silver and Gold Nanoparticles by a Novel Electrochemical Method *ChemPhysChem* **5** 68-75
- [15] Dhand C, Dwivedi N, Loh X J, Jie Ying A N, Verma N K, Beuerman R W, Lakshminarayanan R and Ramakrishna S 2015 Methods and strategies for the synthesis of diverse nanoparticles and their applications: a comprehensive overview *RSC Advances* **5** 105003-37
- [16] Liang W and Harris A T 2011 Facile size and shape control of templated Au nanoparticles under microwave irradiation *Materials Letters* **65** 2307-10
- [17] Marine W, Patrone L, Luk'yanchuk B and Sentis M 2000 Strategy of nanocluster and nanostructure synthesis by conventional pulsed laser ablation *Applied Surface Science* **154–155** 345-52
- [18] Misra N, Biswal J, Gupta A, Sainis J K and Sabharwal S 2012 Gamma radiation induced synthesis of gold nanoparticles in aqueous polyvinyl pyrrolidone solution and its application for hydrogen peroxide estimation *Radiation Physics and Chemistry* **81** 195-200

- [19] Abedini A, Daud A R, Abdul Hamid M A, Kamil Othman N and Saion E 2013 A review on radiation-induced nucleation and growth of colloidal metallic nanoparticles *Nanoscale Research Letters* **8** 474
- [20] Astruc D 2008 *Nanoparticles and catalysis* vol 1: Wiley Online Library
- [21] Conde J, Doria G and Baptista P 2012 Noble Metal Nanoparticles Applications in Cancer *Journal of Drug Delivery* **2012** 12
- [22] Brust M, Fink J, Bethell D, Schiffrin D and Kiely C 1995 Synthesis and reactions of functionalised gold nanoparticles *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.* **16** 1655-6
- [23] Hu J, Zhang J, Liu F, Kittredge K, Whitesell J K and Fox M A 2001 Competitive photochemical reactivity in a self-assembled monolayer on a colloidal gold cluster *Journal of the American Chemical Society* **123** 1464-70
- [24] Ionescu R, Cindemir U, Welearegay T G, Calavia R, Haddi Z, Topalian Z, Granqvist C-G and Llobet E 2017 Fabrication of ultra-pure gold nanoparticles capped with dodecanethiol for Schottky-diode chemical gas sensing devices *Sensors and Actuators B: Chemical* **239** 455-61
- [25] Lansåker P C, Hallén A, Niklasson G A and Granqvist C G 2014 Characterization of gold nanoparticle films: Rutherford backscattering spectroscopy, scanning electron microscopy with image analysis, and atomic force microscopy *AIP Advances* **4** 107101
- [26] Granqvist C and Buhrman R 1976 Ultrafine metal particles *Journal of Applied Physics* **47** 2200-19
- [27] Barash O, Peled N, Hirsch F R and Haick H 2009 Sniffing the unique "odor print" of non-small-cell lung cancer with gold nanoparticles *Small* **5** 2618-24
- [28] Haick H 2007 Chemical sensors based on molecularly modified metallic nanoparticles *Journal of Physics D: Applied Physics* **40** 7173

- [29] Grönbeck H, Curioni A and Andreoni W 2000 Thiols and Disulfides on the Au(111) Surface: The Headgroup–Gold Interaction *Journal of the American Chemical Society* **122** 3839-42
- [30] Gawande M B, Goswami A, Felpin F-X, Asefa T, Huang X, Silva R, Zou X, Zboril R and Varma R S 2016 Cu and Cu-Based Nanoparticles: Synthesis and Applications in Catalysis *Chemical Reviews* **116** 3722-811
- [31] Haitao Z, Canying Z and Yansheng Y 2005 Novel synthesis of copper nanoparticles: influence of the synthesis conditions on the particle size *Nanotechnology* **16** 3079
- [32] Soomro R A, Sherazi S H, Memon N, Shah M, Kalwar N, Hallam K R and Shah A 2014 Synthesis of air stable copper nanoparticles and their use in catalysis *Advanced Materials Letters* **5** 191-8
- [33] Deng Y, Handoko A D, Du Y, Xi S and Yeo B S 2016 In Situ Raman Spectroscopy of Copper and Copper Oxide Surfaces during Electrochemical Oxygen Evolution Reaction: Identification of CuIII Oxides as Catalytically Active Species *ACS Catalysis* **6** 2473-81
- [34] Brust M, Walker M, Bethell D, Schiffrin D J and Whyman R 1994 Synthesis of thiol-derivatised gold nanoparticles in a two-phase Liquid-Liquid system *Journal of the Chemical Society, Chemical Communications* 801-2
- [35] Wuelfing W P, Green S J, Pietron J J, Cliffl D E and Murray R W 2000 Electronic conductivity of solid-state, mixed-valent, monolayer-protected Au clusters *Journal of the American Chemical Society* **122** 11465-72
- [36] Chen S and Sommers J M 2001 Alkanethiolate-protected copper nanoparticles: spectroscopy, electrochemistry, and solid-state morphological evolution *The Journal of Physical Chemistry B* **105** 8816-20

- [37] Joseph Y, Guse B, Vossmeier T and Yasuda A 2008 Gold nanoparticle/organic networks as chemiresistor coatings: the effect of film morphology on vapor sensitivity *The Journal of Physical Chemistry C* **112** 12507-14